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The Effect of Integrating Creative Problem-Solving Process in an “Industry 4.0” Course on College Students’ Creativity

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INTRODUCTION

Industry 4.0 may hold the key to any adaptation to the changing nature of the current state of industries with its potentials to generate, conceptualize, design, and materialize essential ideas surrounding this process. As a high-tech and innovative strategy for the physical production of goods [1], Industry 4.0 is a concept about how to further digitalize the entire value chain of production in the 21st century [2]. Bearing far-reaching influence on the intricate connection that follows among people, objects, and the surrounding systems [2], Industry 4.0 has been widely referred to as the fourth industrial revolution [1]. As the world economy rapidly evolves towards an era of "industry 4.0," an ever-increasing number of studies [3] have focused on effective cultivation of creativity and problem-solving skills among students of higher education. This present study presents an integrated teaching strategy, using four creative strategies: Brainstorming, Six Thinking Hats, SCAMPER, and Bug-List-Technique as well as six stages of creative problem-solving process, to explore relevant implications on teaching and learning about project-based courses in Industry 4.0.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

1.1 Creativity

Creativity drives people to come up with original ideas for potentially workable solutions to problems [5]. It is no longer treated merely as a source of tangible solutions to existing problems; rather, it has transcended and become a set of strategies for a flexible mind set up for all contingencies in an ever changing and increasingly complex world [6, 7]. Recognized as a sequence of thoughts as well as actions for novel and adaptive production [8, 9, 10], this creative process can stimulate problem-solving skills or be mobilized in combination with the said skills towards the development of new products. The emerging prominence of such creative process also propelled Kiesel and Wolpers [11] to list creativity and problem solving as two, out of a total of five, key competences for employees.

1.2 Creative Problem Solving

Knowing the necessity for students to have creative thinking and problem-solving skills upon entering the workplace [12], university program researchers [13, 14, 15] have launched courses on creative problem solving for students such as engineering majors searching for marketable and desirable attributes that meet business demands. Field research [16] featuring job profiles of Information Technology also enlisted

creativity and problem-solving skills as qualifications for Industry 4.0 jobs. Problem solving ability also receives surging popularity from businesses and industries within the field of physical production, the job requirement of which include having been constantly on the change and in which work settings have become increasingly complex and digitized [17]. However, Basadur, Tagaar, and Pringle [18] suggested that creative trainings attempting to achieve further than its framework of thinking are what actually induce new ideas or solutions and truly permeates students' personal creativity. An increasing number of barriers has emerged as research efforts continue to explore such undertaking. As indicated by previous research [19, 20, 21], one of the most common barriers teachers encounter when engaging in such courses is lack of new skills to carry out creative pedagogical approach since few explicit guidelines are available for incorporating creativity into the curriculum and for providing assessment on the impact and effectiveness of their teaching. One possible solution to this challenge was proposed by Titus [22] who invented a 6-stage creative problem solving process as a way to help student develop different phases of creativity. This process inspired the present research to develop a similar creative problem solving (CPS) process as an instructional resource for trainings in creativity among engineering majors.

2 RESEARCH PURPOSE AND QUESTIONS

The purpose of the present research is to explore the influence of the CPS process on creativity among college students when it is used in teaching. This study aims to achieve a successful design of a holistic CPS process, one that is transferable for use in a one-semester course on mechanical engineering. The study also aims to benefit future engineers, who will be solving problems once they go into the workforce of Industry 4.0, which means that creative skills such as identifying potential attributes related to a targeted problem and pinning down probable solutions are crucial.

3 METHOD

3.1 Instructional contexts

Developed by researchers and university instructors in Taiwan, the "Industry 4.0" project-based course is the target of the present research, which employed a 6-staged CPS process and integrated an array of creative thinking strategies such as "Brainstorming", "Six thinking hats", "SCAMPER", and "Bug-List-Technique". Students of this course were required to develop plans, based on the aforementioned creative instructional strategies, for their physical projects related to "industry 4.0" in one of the following six topics: Internet of Things (IoT), big data and cloud computing, cyber-physical systems, embedded systems, sensors, and mechatronics.

3.2 Participants

The research was carried out in the fall semester of 2017 in an “Industry 4.0” project-based course, which featured different trends of learning industry 4.0 as well as their application. The course lasted 18 weeks and included 48 participants (42 male and 6 female), who were assigned to 12 groups according to their chosen topics of the project. Most students in this course majored in mechanical engineering.

3.3 Procedure

Six stages of the CPS process were introduced to the students in sequence across a total of 3 sessions, each of which lasted 3 hours. All of the 3 sessions required students to work the newly learned knowledge at the newly introduced stage into their project. Creative teaching strategies such as Brainstorming, Six Thinking Hats, SCAMPER, and Bug-List-Technique were taught during the course. Each group of students had to complete a worksheet at each stage.

In Huang’s study [23], innovative thinking, which includes cross-categories, multiple-direction, reverse, and originality thinking, and adaptive thinking, which includes mono-category and enriching thinking, are the two constructs for measuring students’ level of divergent and convergent thinking. A subsequent evidence-based evaluation, Revolutionary Drawing, offers a new testing tool, which was adopted in the present study for identifying improvement in students’ level of creativity.

4 RESULTS

A total of forty-eight cases were available for quantitative analysis. Table 1 shows the result of paired sample t-test, which used students’ total scores from the pre and post tests to evaluate their potential progress in creativity. Results indicate a significant improvement ($t=-7.23$, $p<0.001$).

Table 1. The Pair Sample T-test between Pre & Post Total Scores of Creativity Test

	Mean	N	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Total scores(pre)	100.02	48	41.10	-7.23***	0.000
Total scores(post)	167.10	48	63.22		

*** $p<0.001$

Table 2 displays the descriptive statistics of students’ scores in innovative creativity as well as adaptive creativity. Paired sample t-test was adopted both in the analysis of students’ innovative and adaptive creativity. Whereas significant difference ($t=-7.063$, $p<0.001$) was found on innovative creativity, there was no significant difference ($t=-1.864$, $p>0.05$) on adaptive creativity. These findings suggested that students made improvements in terms of innovative creativity but not quite as much in terms of adaptive creativity.

Table 2. The Pair Sample T-test between Pre & Post Innovative Creativity and Adaptive Creativity

	Mean	N	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Innovative Creativity(pre)	98.25	48	40.76	-7.063***	0.000
Innovative Creativity(post)	164.15	48	63.22		
Adaptive Creativity(pre)	1.77	48	2.44	-1.864	0.069
Adaptive Creativity(post)	2.96	48	3.52		

*** $p < 0.001$

Innovative and adaptive creativity are the two constructs of creativity, and innovative creativity includes four types of thinking, cross category thinking, multiple-direction thinking, reverse thinking, and originality, while adaptive creativity includes mono-category thinking and enriching thinking. Paired sample t-test was adopted to analyze how students' creative thinking changed and how the six types of thinking are related to one another through the course. As indicated in Table 3, significant differences were found in terms of innovative creativity, including cross-category thinking ($t = -7.51$, $p < 0.001$), multiple-direction thinking ($t = -2.49$, $p < 0.05$), reverse thinking ($t = -3.23$, $p < 0.01$), and originality ($t = -5.88$, $p < 0.001$). However, no difference was found regarding adaptive thinking, which includes mono-category thinking ($t = 0.00$, $p > 0.05$) and enriching thinking ($t = -0.94$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 3. The Paired Sample T-test between 6 types of thinking

	Mean	N	SD	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
Cross category(pre)	50.00	48	18.33	-7.51***	0.000
Cross category(post)	82.50	48	27.56		
Mono-category(pre)	0.83	48	1.42	0.00	0.092
Mono-category(post)	1.63	48	2.82		
Enriching thinking(pre)	0.94	48	1.92	-0.94	0.354
Enriching thinking(post)	1.33	48	2.09		
Multiple direction thinking(pre)	6.25	48	5.79	-2.49*	0.016
Multiple direction thinking(post)	9.31	48	8.53		
Reverse thinking(pre)	4.81	48	5.80	-3.23**	0.002
Reverse thinking(post)	9.63	48	10.07		
Originality thinking(pre)	37.50	48	18.39	-5.88***	0.000
Originality thinking(post)	62.71	48	29.08		
Total scores(pre)	100.02	48	41.10	-7.23***	0.000
Total scores(post)	167.10	48	63.22		

* $p < 0.05$ ** $p < 0.01$ *** $p < 0.001$

5 DISCUSSION

In the present study, CPS process, which includes problem identification, problem

delineation, information gathering, idea generation, idea evaluation and refinement, and idea implementation, was integrated into an “Industry 4.0” project-based course for researchers to investigate how different types of creativity affect students’ creative performance. Pretest-posttest Revolutionary Drawing was implemented as a tool to evaluate students’ progress in creativity through their participation in the CPS process.

A significant improvement in creativity was found in students’ test results, implying that the application of CPS process had a positive influence on students’ creativity. Results also indicated that different types of divergent thinking are closely associated with one another in their making of innovative creativity. It is also indicated that innovative creativity had a significant impact on students’ total score of creativity. These research findings imply that the CPS process is effective. Students learned to put their imagination into work as groups and were able to generate diverse solutions by thinking out of the box. When interviewed, many students gave credit to the CPS stages, which, they described, “helped them think more systematically.” One student said, for example, “the structure of this course helped me organize many ideas.” Nevertheless, when asked, “which one do you find more difficult, diverging ideas or converging ideas?”, most interviewees chose the latter. One student said, “converging ideas is challenging because we had no means of evaluating the feasibility of ideas generated among ourselves.” Another said, “converging ideas is rather difficult since we often had a hard time separating valuable ideas from bad ones.” We believe that these responses correspond to the non-significant results regarding mono-category thinking and enriching thinking, which are both aspects of adaptive creativity.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of the present study is twofold. First, it explores the influence of the CPS process on creativity among engineering majors in a project-based course on Industry 4.0. In addition, the present research integrated a problem-based learning approach and thematic practice targeted at college students, aiming to enhance creativity through team cooperation. Significant improvement in divergent thinking was found in a paired sample t-test analysis using Revolutionary Drawing. However, no significant improvement was found in students’ convergent thinking. Results indicate that this course design favored students’ innovative creativity over adaptive creativity.

For future research, we suggest more varied CPS methodologies to be employed to extend choices and varieties available for as many aspects of creativity as possible in order to be applied in more diverse programs and course designs in college.

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